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Attitudes, Perception, and Acceptance of the Covid-19 Vaccine Among Primary Healthcare Workers in Calabar Municipality, Cross River State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Primary healthcare workers (PHCWs) play a pivotal role in pandemic response and vaccine advocacy, yet vaccine hesitancy remains a public health challenge globally. In Nigeria, misinformation, sociocultural beliefs, and limited health literacy threaten vaccine uptake. This study aimed to assess attitudes, perceptions, and acceptance of the COVID-19 vaccine among PHCWs in Calabar Municipality, and to identify key factors influencing their uptake. A cross-sectional descriptive survey was conducted in 2022 among 152 PHCWs using a semi-structured, self-administered questionnaire. Respondents were selected using convenience sampling. Quantitative data were analyzed with SPSS version 23 to determine descriptive statistics, including frequencies and percentages. Attitudes and perceptions were assessed using Likert scales and categorized into positive or negative groups based on predefined thresholds. Of the 152 participants, 133 (87%) had received at least one dose of the COVID-19 vaccine. Among them, 42.8% had received the first, second, and booster doses. Positive attitudes and perceptions were observed in 84% and 78% of respondents, respectively. Vaccine uptake was mainly driven by personal conviction (66.4%), while other motivating factors included trust in health authorities (15.1%), peer influence (9.2%), and media exposure (8.6%). Barriers to uptake included concerns about vaccine safety (26.3%), religious beliefs (21.7%), conspiracy theories (16.4%), and mistrust in government information significantly hindered uptake (11.8%). Vaccine acceptance among PHCWs in Calabar Municipality is relatively high but remains undermined by misinformation and sociocultural concerns. Targeted interventions such as health literacy campaigns, trust-building with health authorities, and culturally tailored communication strategies are recommended to improve vaccine confidence and sustain high uptake rates.

Keywords: COVID-19 vaccine, Vaccine uptake, Health worker attitudes, Perception; Acceptance, Nigeria, Vaccine hesitancy, Calabar

1. INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic, caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), has had profound global impacts on healthcare systems, economies, and education (Lenzen et al., 2020). As of 2021, there were over 271 million confirmed cases and 5.3 million deaths worldwide. The virus, which originated in Wuhan, China, primarily affects the respiratory system, with symptoms ranging from mild rhinorrhea to severe respiratory distress syndrome (WHO, 2021).

Vulnerable populations, including the elderly and those with comorbidities such as hypertension and diabetes, face higher mortality risks (Bhatraju et al., 2020; Grasselli et al., 2020). In Africa, where healthcare systems are under-resourced, the pandemic has exacerbated existing challenges, with limited infrastructure and delayed vaccine access increasing the risk of widespread transmission (Elhadi et al., 2020).

Vaccination remains the most effective strategy to control the pandemic, yet its success hinges on public acceptance. Despite global efforts, vaccine hesitancy persists, fueled by misinformation and conspiracy theories (Kumar et al., 2016; Paterson et al., 2016). Healthcare workers (HCWs), who are at high risk of infection due to direct patient contact, play a critical role in shaping public perception and vaccine uptake (Chou et al., 2020). However, studies reveal varying acceptance rates among HCWs globally. For instance, in Egypt, only 21% of HCWs accepted the vaccine, while in South Africa, acceptance was as high as 90% (Samar et al., 2021; Oladele et al., 2021). In Nigeria, where the government prioritized HCWs for vaccination, concerns about safety, side effects, and distrust in authorities have hindered uptake (Adejumo et al., 2021).

The Health Belief Model (HBM) provides a useful framework for understanding vaccine hesitancy, emphasizing perceived susceptibility, severity, benefits, and barriers (Lipman & Burt, 2017). Prior research highlights that HCWs' attitudes and perceptions significantly influence their vaccination decisions and recommendations to patients (Nzaji et al., 2020). Negative perceptions, often stemming from inadequate information or fear of side effects, can undermine immunization efforts (Verger et al., 2015). For example, in Pakistan, 70% of HCWs accepted the vaccine, but concerns about efficacy and side effects were prominent among those who hesitated (Malik et al, 2021). Similarly, in Saudi Arabia, 55% of respondents cited safety concerns as a key barrier (Magadmi & Kamel, 2021).

This study focuses on primary healthcare workers in Calabar Municipality, Nigeria, a group pivotal to pandemic response yet underrepresented in existing literature. By assessing their attitudes, perceptions, and acceptance of the COVID-19 vaccine, the study aims to identify barriers and inform targeted interventions. The findings will contribute to strategies for improving vaccine uptake among HCWs, ultimately enhancing pandemic control in resource-limited settings. The research employs a cross-sectional design, utilizing surveys to gather data from 152 participants, with analysis conducted using SPSS version 23. Key outcomes include vaccine uptake rates, factors influencing acceptance, and recommendations for policy and practice.

In summary, this study addresses a critical gap in understanding vaccine hesitancy among Nigerian HCWs, offering insights to bolster public health efforts. By aligning findings with the HBM and comparing them to global trends, the research underscores the need for culturally sensitive education and trust-building measures to combat misinformation and promote vaccination.

2. METHODS

2. 1. Study Area

The study area was Calabar Municipality, Cross River State. Calabar municipal is a local government area in Cross river state and serves as the state capital. The Local Government Area has 12 political wards and each ward has at least 1 Primary Healthcare center. Calabar Municipal is bordered by the Kwa, Calabar Rivers, Odukpani, and Calabar south L.G.A. It has an area of 142 km², the population of Calabar Municipal LGA is estimated at 187,432 inhabitants with the majority of the area's dwellers being members of the Efik and the Qua ethnic divisions. Christianity is the widely practiced religion in the LGA Whilst the Efik, Qua, and English languages are commonly spoken in the area. Trading, industrial activities, and civil services occupations are the key economic activity in the Calabar Municipal. According to the primary healthcare Nominal roll in Calabar municipal (March 2022), they have a total number of 245 primary healthcare workers across different wards in the local government. the different cadre includes 31 junior CHEW, 113 senior CHEW, 10 CHO, 56 medical laboratory technicians, 2 pharmacy technicians, 8 Nurses, 4 medical laboratory recorders, 17 Environmental, and 2 drivers.

2. 2. Scope of the study

The study was carried out among staff of Primary Healthcare Centres in Calabar municipality.

2. 3. Study Design

This study adopted a cross-sectional descriptive study design using a quantitative method of data collection.

2. 4. Study population

The population from this study included all essential primary healthcare workers in Calabar municipality L.G.A

2. 5. Sample size determination

The sample size of the study was determined using: Taron Yaman's formula. This formula is used when the sample size of a target population is small.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N \times (e)^2}$$

where:

n = the sample size (population)
N = the population size (Total population)
e = the acceptable sampling error

Therefore

$$n = \frac{245}{1+245 \times (0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{245}{1 + 245 \times 0.0025}$$

$$n = \frac{245}{1 + 0.6125}$$

$$n = \frac{245}{1.6125}$$

$$n = 151.93798114.28 \text{ approx. } 152$$

The final sample size is 152.

2. 6. Sampling procedures

Convenience sampling method were used in which any available healthcare staff in the PHC within the municipality was sampled. The sample were drawn from a sampling frame. The convenience sampling technique is preferred due to the availability and number of health workers in the primary Healthcare Centers in the chosen LGA. 18% was used to determine the inclusion and exclusion criteria from each cadre of the primary healthcare workers.

2. 7. Instruments for data collection

The instrument for data collection were semi-structured questionnaire, which was divided into sections and data was collected on different aspects of the study. The first section of the study covered the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents. The subsequent sections collected data on each of the specific objective variables.

2. 8. Pre-testing

Pre-testing of the instrument were done using (5% of the sample size) in selected Primary Healthcare centres in Calabar South. Calabar South shares similar characteristics with Calabar municipal. Pre-testing helped to check the reliability and validity of the tool. It also helped in determining the relevance of questions and variables under measurement, remove ambiguity where it exists, train field assistants on how best to capture sensitive questions, and estimate the maximum time for completion of questions.

2. 9. Method of data collection

Data was collected using self-administered questionnaire. The researcher or the field

assistants introduced themselves, and the study obtained consent from the individual, before handing over the questionnaire. Two research assistants were engaged in administering the questionnaire. Respondents were given room to ask questions for more clarity for unclear questions during data collection.

2. 10. Methods of data analysis

Data was analysed for this study; descriptive statistics were used from the completed questionnaire. Data generated were analysed using the statistical package for social science [SPSS] version 23, results were presented in simple percentages, table, Figs, and charts using MS word. The Response was coded into scores (Yes = 1, No = 2, I don't know = 3) with other questions in its variables and summed for each respondent, then the total scores were categorized positive or Negative for those questions that has to deal with the variable.

2. 11. Ethical considerations

A letter of introduction was obtained from the Department of Public Health, University of Calabar, and was used to apply for ethical clearance from Ministry of Primary health development Agency, Cross River State. The respondents were informed about the research and its procedures. They were also assured that their participation is voluntary and they can opt-out at any time. In addition, the respondents' confidentiality and anonymity will be maintained. Verbal informed consent was obtained from all the respondents before the administration of the study questionnaire.

3. RESULTS

3. 1. Socio-demographic characteristics of respondents

One hundred and fifty-two (152) questionnaires were administered and the same was retrieved by the researcher accounting for a response rate of 100%. The socio-demographic data of respondents shows that a total of 39(25.7%) were males Whilst 113(74.3%) were females. The mean age of respondents was 39.40(±9.1). However, under the age category 86(56.6%) were between the age of 20-40, 66(43.4%) were within the age of >40. Based on marital status, 49(25.7%) were single, 88(57.9%) were married, 7(4.6%) were separated, 2(1.3%) were divorced, 1(0.7%) were widower, 5(3.3%) were widow. Under the religion category, 142(93.4%) were Christian, 5(3.3%) were Islam, 4(2.6%) were traditionalist and 1(0.7%) of the respondents did not belong to any of the religions. The respondents were seen to have varying proportion of educational qualifications. Of the 152 respondents, 17(11.2%) had master Degree, 58(38.2%) had B.sc, 55(36.2%) had HND, 19(12.5%) had ND, 3(2.0) had NCE.

Meanwhile, the Years of experiences of the respondents were also determined and according to the report out of 152 of the respondents 37(24.3%) had worked 0-5 years, 60(39.5%) had also worked 6-10 years, and 55(36.2%) had worked >10 years. Respondent also had different levels of job role were 14(9.2%) were Nurse, 16(10.5%) were Nurse/CHO, 29(19.1%) were CHO, 46(30.3%) were Sen. Chew, 17(11.2%) were J-Chew, 6(3.9%) were medical Records, 6(3.9%) were pharmacy Technicians, 7(4.6%) were medical Laboratory Technicians, 11(7.2) were Environmental Health officer and 1(0.7%) were Date Entry Claret.

The results of socio-demographics are represented in Table 1.

Table 1. Socio-demographic characteristics of respondents.

Variable	Frequency (n = 152)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	39	25.7
Female	113	74.3
Age Category (39.4±9.1)		
Youthful age (20-40)	86	56.6
Elderly (>40)	66	43.4
Marital Status		
Single	49	32.2
Married	88	57.9
Separated	7	4.6
Divorced	2	1.3
Widower	1	0.7
Widow	5	3.3
Religion		
Christianity	142	93.4
Islam	5	3.3
Traditional	4	2.6
Others	1	0.7
Highest level of education		
Master Degree	17	11.2
B.Sc	58	38.2
HND	55	36.2
ND	19	12.5
NCE	3	2.0
Years of experiences		
0-5	37	24.3
6-10	60	39.5
>10	55	36.2

Job role		
Nurse	14	9.2
Nurse/CHO	16	10.51q
CHO/89	29	19.1
Sen. Chew	46	30.3
J-Chew	17	11.2
Medical Records	6	3.9
Pharmacy Technicians	6	3.6
Medical Laboratory Technicians	7	4.6
Environmental Health Officer	11	7.2
Date Entry Claret	1	0.7

p < 0.05

3. 2. Uptake/Acceptance of Covid-19 among primary healthcare workers

Regarding vaccine uptake, majority of the respondents 133(87%) had taken the vaccine against a few 19(13%) who had not taken the vaccine at all (Figure 3). However, out of 133(87%) of the respondents that have taken the vaccine, 65(42.8%), 47(30.9%), and 21(13.8%) had received 1st, 2nd, and booster shots, respectively (Figure 4).

3. 3. Attitudes of respondents towards the Uptake and acceptance of the Covid-19 vaccine

Regarding attitudes to COVID-19 vaccine, 127(84%) of the respondents had positive attitudes toward the vaccine Whilst 25(16%) had negative attitudes on a 2-point Likert scale was used to evaluate the attitudes level of covid-19 vaccination among the respondents . This is calculated by assigning scores of 0, and 1 to the response categories, respectively, of „YES”, „NO”, with a score above 4/7 considered to be a positive attitudes score and a score below that considered to be a negative attitudes was used to determine the attitude level of the respondents. (Figure 5, Table 2).

3. 4. Acceptance of the Covid-19 vaccine among primary healthcare workers

Acceptance of Covid-19 vaccine shows that 101(66.4%) of the 133(87%) who had taken the vaccine reported that it was their personal decision and out of its necessity and importance. However, 25(16.4%), and 7(4.6%), took the vaccine because it was made compulsory by the health agency and government and because they felt their job was threatened if there did not take it (Figure 6).

Other factors that may have influenced the respondent’s Acceptance of the covid-19 vaccine were seen to be unavailability of adequate information to make an informed decision about the vaccine 46(30.30%), those who took the vaccine based on perceived fatality of those

infected with the disease were 27(17.80%), 23(15.10%) took the vaccine because they trusted the information given by the government and health authorities on the safety of the vaccine, while 9.20% took the vaccine because their senior colleagues took it. Furthermore, 13(8.60%) of the respondents took the vaccine because there was enough and trusted information in the different media on the vaccine, while 8(5.30%) took the vaccine because reputable companies and organization were involved in the vaccine production and finally, 2(1.3%) took the vaccine because they were compelled to do so. (Figure 7).

3. 5. Perceptions of respondents towards the Covid-19 vaccine

Assessment of perception toward the covid-19 vaccination. A 3-point Likert scale was used to evaluate the perception level of covid-19 vaccination among the respondents. This is calculated by assigning scores of 0, 1, and 2 to the response categories, respectively, of „YES”, „NO”, „I DON’T KNOW”. A benchmark score of 12/20 were considered to be a positive perception Whilst anything below that is considered a negative perception. Out of 152 respondents that was sampled, 118(78%) had a positive perception toward the vaccine Whilst 34(22%) had a negative perception toward the vaccine (Figure 8, Table 3).

3. 6. Factors that influenced the respondents’ decision toward the uptake of the covid-19 vaccine

Considering factors influencing uptake, 40(26.30%) of respondents were of the opinion that the potential side effects/complications of the vaccine negatively influenced uptake. Other factors include, religious belief 33(21.70%), concern about the uncertainty and conspiracy theories about the vaccine 25(16.40%), fear of needles 20(13.20%), uncertainty about some political undertone about the vaccine 18(11.80%), however, 9(5.90%) don’t believe that covid-19 is real, Whilst 7(4.60%) of the respondents had other reasons toward non-acceptance and uptake of the vaccine (Figure 9).

Respondents also had concerns about the COVID-19 disease which is thought to influence uptake. Out of 152 respondents that were sampled, 59(38.80%) were concerned about the origin of the disease, 54(35.50%) were concerned about the inability of the health system to cope with the disease, 29(19.10%) were concerned about the fatality and mortality rates attributed to the disease to be exaggerated for political gains, Whilst 10(6.60%) believed that the disease is not real and is politically motivated (Figure 10).

Table 2. Attitudes of respondents towards the Covid-19 vaccine.

Variable	Frequency (n = 152)	Percentage (%)
Do you think covid-19 is a severe disease that may cause severe complications?		
Yes	132	86.8
No	20	13.2

Do you see the vaccine as a good approach to fighting the covid-19 virus?		
Yes	137	90.1
No	15	9.9
Do you believe that vaccination benefits outweigh the risk?		
Yes	125	82.2
No	27	17,8
Will you willingly take the covid-19 vaccine without any hesitation?		
Yes	117	77.0
No	35	23.0
Will you encourage/advise friends and family to get vaccinated against covid-19?		
Yes	134	88.2
No	18	11.8
Are you of the opinion that the covid-19 vaccine for health care workers should be mandatory as a means of controlling the disease?		
Yes	106	69.7
No	45	29.6
Do you trust the advice given by the government and health agency about covid-19 vaccine?		
Yes	132	86.8
No	20	13.2

Table 3. Perception of respondents towards the Covid-19 vaccine.

Variable	Frequency (n = 152)	Percentage (%)
Do you think it's important to get vaccinated?		
Yes	127	83.6
No	17	11.2
I don't Know	8	5.3
Do you think front-line health workers should be a priority population to be vaccinated during vaccine preventable epidemic/pandemic as a way of controlling the spread?		
Yes	126	82.9
No	17	11.2
I don't Know	9	5.9
Do you think the covid-19 vaccine is effective in preventing/controlling the covid-19 vaccine?		
Yes	118	77.6
No	19	12.5
I don't Know	15	9.9
I don't believe in the covid-19 vaccine.		
Yes	36	23.7
No	99	65.1
I don't know	17	11.2
Do you think you are at risk of becoming infected with covid-19?		
Yes	77	50.7
No	61	40.1
I don't know	14	9.2

Do you think that the development of covid-19 vaccine was properly carried out to make them safe?		
Yes	92	60.5
No	28	18.4
I don't know	32	21.1
Are you worried about possible complications that may arise from uptake of covid-19 vaccine?		
Yes	78	51.3
No	69	45.4
I don't know	5	3.3
Do you think that the covid-19 vaccine can worsen any health conditions you have?		
Yes	61	40.1
No	69	45.4
I don't know	22	14.5
Do you think the numbers of the reported cases of covid-19 are being exaggerated?		
Yes	60	39.5
No	50	32.9
I don't know	42	27.6
The whole idea about covid-19 vaccine is all lies?		
Yes	32	21.1
No	85	55.9
I don't know	35	23.0

Figure 1. Covid-19 vaccine uptake of the respondents.

Figure 2. Percentage of covid-19 vaccine shot received by the interviewers.

Figure 3. Percentage response on Attitude of interviewers towards Covid-19 vaccine.

Figure 4. Percentage response of interviewers on decision towards Acceptance Covid-19 vaccine.

Figure 5. Other factors that influenced respondents' decisions toward covid-19 vaccine acceptances.

Figure 6. Percentage response on Perception of interviewers towards Covid-19 vaccine.

Figure 7. Factors that influenced the uptake of a covid-19 vaccine by the respondents.

Figure 8. Concerns of the respondents about the disease (covid-19).

4. DISCUSSION

4. 1. Acceptance of the covid-19 vaccine among primary healthcare workers in Calabar municipality L.G.A.

Findings show that most of participants were vaccine accepting which shows high level of uptake (87%) but Environment health officers who were 11 in number but only (45.5%) had received the Covid-19 vaccine and had the lowest Acceptance rate, this may be due to lack of Knowledge about Covid-19 virus among them, and also majority of those who have taken the vaccine, (42.8%) have received 1st, 2nd and booster shot. However, majority of the respondents who took vaccine did that out of their own self well, those who took the vaccine because it was made compulsory by the health agency/government and because they felt their job was threatened if there did not take it.

This high rate of vaccine acceptance was comparable to the findings of earlier studies conducted by Samar et al., (2021) on the Attitudes toward COVID-19 vaccination among healthcare workers in which Most of the participants were vaccine-accepting. Additionally, a recent study conducted by Koh et al., (2022) & Youssef et al, (2022) result showed a high percentage of vaccine accepting in which the respondents believed that covid-19 vaccine acceptance was a condition in which there would continue working. However, this study is in contrast with a recent meta-analysis of studies on primary healthcare workers by Zammit et al., in the study, however, were shown to be hesitant to receive the COVID-19 vaccine. In a global study that was conducted in 12 countries, the majority of participants were in favor of vaccinations; nevertheless, Egypt and African nations had the lowest vaccination acceptance rates because they believed that vaccination benefits outweigh the risk and lack of trust in the advice given by the government and health agency about the covid-19 vaccine. (Noushad et al., 2022). In the Republic of Congo, it was observed that only (27.7%) of staff working in healthcare settings would agree to obtain the COVID-19 vaccine. Discrepancies in vaccine acceptance between these regions may be attributed to false information on social media platforms (Klugar, Riad, Mohanan, & Pokorná, 2021).

4. 2. Attitudes of primary healthcare workers toward covid-19 vaccine in Calabar municipality L.G.A.

Healthcare Workers are more likely to contract COVID-19 than the general population. So, their attitudes toward vaccination are crucial since it can determine how well the general population responds to it (Shehata et al., 2022). From the findings of this study, it shows that Everionmental health Officers had the lowest attitudes compared to other cadre, meanwhile, (84%) of the total respondents had positive attitudes toward the vaccine which means that the vaccine has a great impact on the healthcare workers. It was identified that majority of the resopondents who have a positive or negative attitudes toward the vaccine believed that covid-19 is a severe disease that may cause severe complications, vaccine is a good approach to fighting the covid-19 virus, And that vaccination benefits outweigh the risk. Findings show majority agreed that they will encourage/advise friends and family to get vaccinated against covid-19.

Nevertheless, (69.7%) believed that covid-19 vaccine for healthcare workers should be mandatory as a means of controlling the disease also, high number of them believed in the advice given by the government and health agency about covid-19 vaccine. This study is in line with a study conducted on Knowledge, attitudes, and perceptions of the COVID-19 vaccine and

refusal to receive the COVID-19 vaccine in which the overall positive attitudes rate about the COVID-19 vaccine was (52.3%) (Wouters et al., 2021). Additionally, this study is comparable with a study conducted by Samar et al., (2021) in which majority (85.7%) had positive toward the vaccine against the few with negative attitudes. (79.8%) of vaccine acceptant group agreed that covid-19 vaccine should be made compulsory for healthcare workers and at high risk of contracting the virus. They also agreed that they're at high risk of the covid-19 adverse event and that, covid-19 is a serious disease that may cause serious complications.

4. 3. Perception of primary healthcare workers toward covid-19 vaccine in Calabar municipality L.G.A.

Findings from this study shows the overall rate of positive/negative perception about the COVID-19 vaccine by primary healthcare workers in which Environmental health officers has the lowest level of perception followed by Nurse/CHO, majority of the respondents had a positive perception toward the vaccine which show a high level of good perception toward the covid-19 and its vaccine, (83.6%) believed that getting vaccinated is important, that front-line health workers should be a priority population to be vaccinated during vaccine preventable epidemic/pandemic as a means of controlling the, majority agreed that covid-19 vaccine is effective in preventing/controlling the covid-19 virus against which shows their believe towards the vaccine. They were concerned about the high risk of getting effected by covid-19 virus and possible complications that may arise from the uptake of the vaccine, Meanwhile, many of them agreed on the development of covid-19 vaccine was properly done.

It was gathered that many of the respondents believed that Covid-19 vaccine could worsen any health conditions and the number of reported cases are being exaggerated by the media which makes them to think that Covid-19 virus are all lie from the government. Consistent with prior findings from Ethiopia (Wouters et al., 2021) on Knowledge, attitudes, and perceptions of the COVID-19 vaccine and refusal to receive the COVID-19 vaccine among healthcare workers in north-eastern Ethiopia in which the overall rate of good perception about the COVID-19 vaccine was high.

Three-quarters of the healthcare workers considered themselves to be at high risk of becoming infected with COVID-19 and 39.5% of them thought that they could get infected with COVID-19 through vaccination. Similarly, nearly half of the healthcare workers thought that vaccines could worsen any pre-existing medical conditions. On the other hand, (44.1%) of the respondents thought that it may not be possible to reduce the incidence of COVID-19 without vaccination. This study is in contrast with a study carried out which show that minority healthcare workers are feeling safer one year into the COVID-19 pandemic, but approximately one out of every four healthcare workers did not take the COVID-19 vaccine even when they had access to it (Price-Haywood, Burton, Fort, & Seoane, 2020).

4. 4. Factors influencing uptake of covid-19 vaccine among primary healthcare workers in Calabar municipality L.G.A.

Refusal to be vaccinated for the Covid-19 vaccine was significantly associated with a negative attitudes and negative perception. Healthcare workers who had negative attitudes about COVID-19 vaccines 3.06 times refused to be vaccinated compared to those who had a positive attitude toward COVID-19 vaccines. Furthermore, Healthcare workers who had a negative perception about COVID-19 vaccines 4.73 times refused to be vaccinated compared

to those who had a positive perception toward COVID-19 vaccines. Findings from this study identified the following factors to have influenced the respondents uptake of the Covid-19 vaccine; potential side effects/complications and its safety of the vaccine, religion, uncertainty and conspiracy about the vaccine coming from health professionals, others thinks that there is some political undertone about the vaccine and fatality and mortality rates are exaggerated for political gains which makes them to believe that Covid-19 is not real, fear of needles, concern about the origin of the disease and inability of the health system to cope with the disease, fast rate at which the vaccine was manufactured and approved for use, and that covid-19 vaccine is a means in which population control/starling from the west will be achieved. In the Republic of Congo, it was observed that only 27.7% of staff working in healthcare settings would agree to obtain the COVID-19 vaccine.

Discrepancies in vaccine acceptance between these regions may be attributed to false information on social media platforms (Klugar et al., 2021). Study conducted by Machingaidze & Wiysonge, (2021) show that majority of respondents were strongly dependent on social media as a COVID-19 news outlet, which is a source of inconsistent and incomplete information during the pandemic and distrusted the credibility of COVID-19 vaccine information issued by the Sudanese government. Additionally, a Bivariate analysis conducted by Wouters et al., (2021) on Knowledge, attitudes, and perceptions of the COVID-19 vaccine and refusal to receive COVID-19 the following factors was identified; absence of COVID-19 in the family or among colleagues and friends, failure to be tested for COVID-19, failure to obtain training or orientation about COVID-19 vaccination, negative attitudes, and poor knowledge and perception.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This descriptive cross-sectional study of 152 primary healthcare workers in Calabar Municipality reveals a compelling paradox in COVID-19 vaccine acceptance. While 87% had received vaccination with 66.4% making this decision independently, a concerning 44.1% expressed doubts about COVID-19's reality, exposing a striking disconnect between professional practice and personal conviction.

The research demonstrates predominantly positive attitudes (84%) and perceptions (78%) toward COVID-19 vaccines, with 42.8% completing their full vaccination series including booster doses. However, primary barriers persisted: inadequate access to comprehensive information for informed decision-making (30.3%), concerns about potential adverse effects and complications (26.3%), perceived inadequacy of the health system's capacity to manage the pandemic (35.5%), and religious beliefs conflicting with vaccination (21.7%).

These findings illuminate that high vaccination rates may be driven by professional obligations rather than genuine acceptance of the vaccine's necessity and safety. The coexistence of high uptake with substantial doubts suggests social pressures and professional requirements beyond personal conviction influenced vaccine acceptance.

Primary healthcare workers serve as crucial intermediaries between health authorities and the general population, functioning as both vaccine administrators and trusted sources of health information. Their attitudes and perceptions significantly influence community acceptance of vaccination programs, making the identification of negative attitudes and perceptions as

primary determinants of vaccine refusal particularly concerning for sustainable vaccination efforts.

In conclusion, while the moderately high uptake among primary healthcare workers in Calabar Municipality is encouraging, the persistence of negative attitudes and perceptions represents a significant challenge for sustained public health efforts. The study demonstrates that vaccine acceptance involves complex interactions between personal beliefs, access to information, trust in health systems, and cultural factors. Addressing these multifaceted concerns through comprehensive, culturally appropriate interventions is essential for maintaining high vaccination rates among healthcare workers and ensuring their effectiveness as advocates for vaccination in their communities.

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